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An iterative model for the design of contextualised innovation indicators: experimentation oriented to food security development goals in South Africa

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Introduction

A major gap in the innovation measurement literature is systematic critical reflection, refinement and adaptations of the standard indicator models to the socio-economic conditions and innovation challenges of middle and low income African countries in the global South (Kruss 2018; Gault 2020; Iizuka and Hollanders 2017). Standard innovation indicators were primarily developed in high income country contexts, based on national business innovation survey datasets, through a measurement endeavour that evolved over decades, to create a significant degree of global comparability and hard won rigor (Godin 2015).

There is also recognition, that if the main purpose of innovation indicators is to assess changes and progress towards the attainment of policy goals, then, as global sustainability challenges have become more complex and more difficult to resolve, and as the inequality gaps between and within countries have widened, the value and applicability of the dominant innovation measurement frameworks must be critically revisited, and extended (Cocos and Lepori 2019; Cirera and Muzi 2020; Rafols 2019; Klarin 2019; Lepori et al 2008; Dziallas and Blind 2019; Das et al 2012).

The challenge now is to find the ideal balance between generalisable innovation indicators that allow comparability between national innovation systems, and contextually oriented indicators that can guide a mix of policy interventions (Borras and Edler 2020) at multiple levels:

... indicators are needed to support the strategic decisions of actors...and to help to improve the autonomous coordination of the system, rather than to provide to the national state the information to control and steer the system (Lepori et al 2008: 42).

As yet, there is not a substantial body of contributions to the task, and there is much room for conceptualising and designing workable alternatives. How can new indicators build on the rigor and validity of standardized measures, but retain context specific relevance and utility for policy makers?

The paper reflects on a process of inductive and deductive experimentation to design new innovation indicators, in the South African context. It identifies dimensions, measures and data sources that build on standard Oslo business innovation survey models (OECD 2018), to

create evidence for new innovation policy mixes (Borras and Edler 2020; Cocos and Lepori 2020) oriented to address complex societal challenges, in this case, the SDG goal of food security and eradicating hunger.

Brief overview of development challenges

South Africa is a resource rich, formerly colonised African country caught in a middle income trap for more than seventy years (Kruss 2020; Oqubayi 2021; Andreoni et al 2021). With the highest rate of inequality in the world, the majority of citizens experience high rates of unemployment and poverty, while a small elite benefits economically, politically and socially. The economy requires structural transformation, given the ongoing reliance on mineral resources, the decline of manufacturing sectors and the growth of services sectors, both tradeable and non-tradeable (Andreoni et al 2021; Oqubay et al 2021). The national system of innovation is characterised by ‘islands of excellence’ of globally competitive science and technology capabilities, but is challenged to put new or improved knowledge to use, to shift socio-economic challenges. Innovation policy since 1994 is committed to dual development goals of economic growth and human development, but the policy mix and indicators adopted are strongly akin to high income countries (Walwyn and Naidoo 2020).

A pragmatic, experimental and reflective model for indicator design

This section demonstrates the innovation indicator design model that emerged from and can be used to experiment. Through a reflective iterative process, conceptual, policy, methodological and empirical distinctions were identified, integrated and synthesised, as set out in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. A pragmatic, reflective and experimental approach

The model begins from a commitment to tackle development challenges, which in the South African case, can be summarised as an innovation policy mix to promote inclusive and sustainable development. A specific focal challenge is selected, in this case, SDG 2 goal of eradicating hunger and ensuring food security (Step 2). ‘Sectoral’ expertise is needed to understand the innovation challenges in the focal area. In this case, a conceptual model of the

food system was adopted (Burger 2020), distinguishing four sub-systems: food production, processing, distribution and consumption (Step 3). Each has distinct production, value chain and innovation dynamics, and may involve enterprises of different sizes and degrees of formality, with distinctive patterns of innovation activity and support needs.

In this paper, it was only possible to focus experimentation on the agricultural food production system (red quadrant).

Innovation policy analysis to extract key policy intents (Step 4) related to agricultural production are identified and key policy concepts defined. Ideally, this step requires the active involvement of policy actors at multiple levels, to ensure policy intent is captured appropriately, to provide high-level criteria for the selection of indicators.

However, there is little point in designing an indicator framework if there are no datasets to operationalise it. A crucial iterative step is to assess the available and accessible datasets, in terms of coverage, dimensions and variables (Step 5). To complement innovation data, a scan of available administrative data (for example, innovation or R&D grants databases), and other national datasets (for example, labour force surveys) is required.

The most conceptually and technically demanding step, 6, is to design indicators and measures oriented to the policy intent. An analytical approach proposed by Arundel (2006) was adopted, which aims to design indicators of greater policy value using business innovation datasets. Arundel experimented with indicators that map *how enterprises innovate*, informed by policy demands in a specific context (Hollanders and Arundel 2007; Arundel and O'Brien 2009). Mapping empirical patterns of innovation and linkages across sets of firms can inform the alignment of policy instruments with existing activities and capabilities in a national or sectoral system of innovation, and track progress towards desired policy change over time.

Step 7 requires reflective engagement to evaluate and assess the indicator scheme and measures, and variables that can be adapted or added without incurring huge costs or breaking time series.

The next two sections zoom in to focus in greater detail on experimentation in steps 4 to 6.

Policy intents and datasets in the food system space

Table 1 below summarises the proposed indicator scheme, informed by contextualised analysis of policy intent (4) and data accessibility (5).

Working definitions of core policy commitments were used to conduct a search of the *Decadal Plan on Science, Technology and Innovation 2021/2*, to identify policy intents specifically related to the food system, sustainability, agriculture and inclusion (step 4).

To define sustainability was relatively simple, given that the UN definition is encapsulated as a core value mainstreamed throughout the South African innovation policy documents:

...a paradigm for thinking about the future in which environmental, societal and economic considerations are balanced in the pursuit of an improved quality of life (<https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-sustainable-development/what-is-esd/sd>).

To define inclusive development, a three-fold distinction increasingly used in policy analysis was adopted: industrial, territorial and social inclusion (Planes-Satoria and Paunov 2017). In

terms of *industrial inclusion*, the policy objective is to enhance economy-wide innovation and technological capabilities, across sectors, firm sizes, local or global ownership, and formal and informal enterprises. Policy objectives to promote *territorial inclusiveness* aim to narrow the gaps between metropolitan areas where resources are typically concentrated, to include towns, cities and villages in rural and isolated areas, as well as impoverished urban areas like townships and informal settlements. *Social inclusiveness* is the commitment that innovation should contribute to ‘prevent deepening and exacerbation of inequality’, a dimension not typically included in surveys.

These dimensions are inter-twined and not separable in real life, but using them to analyse the policy documents enabled identification of three main policy priorities in the food system space that frame innovation problems, for which new indicators are required:

- Technological upgrading to modernize and strengthen agricultural production for export and to grow jobs in a sustainable manner
- Technological upgrading and capability building for sustainable local economic development through agriculture and agro-processing in rural, township and peri-urban areas
- Technological upgrading and capability building for sustainable food distribution and consumption livelihoods, and access to food and nutrition in vulnerable communities

The experimental design in the next section focuses on the first policy intent, given the ready availability and accessibility of datasets:

- A new Oslo-based (OECD 2018) dataset of innovation in formal agricultural enterprises (AgriBIS) that included sectorally customised new measures, of the adoption of digital technologies, and of sustainability outcomes (CeSTII 2021)
- A national census of commercial agricultural production (StatsSA 2020)
- National statistics on export, employment patterns and job creation

An experimental indicator framework

Table 1 below proposes a set of indicators to assess how patterns of enterprise innovation in the agricultural production system promote policy goals over time. The six dimensions were extracted from the policy intent:

Technological upgrading and adoption of advanced technologies (2), adapted to local climate and environmental conditions (4), to ‘modernise’ (2) and strengthen existing productive sectors (3), in order to grow exports (5) and grow jobs (6), by more firms in the agricultural sector (1).

It is relatively easy to design indicators and metrics for Dimensions 1, 5 and 6, using national statistics. For example, there is good longitudinal data available to track changes in agricultural employment (by job levels and by spatial location) to measure the policy outcome of growth in jobs over time, in a way that reflects shifts in social and territorial inclusion.

Likewise, simple proxy indicators of sustainability outcomes can be designed using an item in the AgriBIS that assesses whether an enterprise’s innovation activity has reduced the negative effects of climate change, in four areas: biodiversity, water preservation, soil fertility or reduced greenhouse gas. Measures can be created in a number of ways, depending on purpose:

- Scale: shifts in the number of non/innovative enterprises reporting each outcome
- Intensity: shifts in the number of sustainability outcomes achieved by each non/innovative enterprise

- Industrial and territorial inclusion: categories such as firm size or spatial location used to map patterns of sustainability outcomes
- Composite measure: a scale of low to high innovation sustainability at a systemic level

Greater complexity and more detailed experimentation is required to design metrics of modernisation and strengthening of the agricultural production system (Dimensions 2 and 3). Two sets of proxy indicators of technological upgrading were tested – one that assesses science and technology intensity by defining modes of innovation activity, and one that assesses the adoption of new advanced digital technologies¹. Usually, simple modes of innovation such as product or process are reported, but these are of limited utility to the policy maker assessing agricultural modernisation. Appropriate metrics (degree of novelty or type of activity) can be used to define contextually relevant modes of innovation, sufficiently fine-grained to assess changes in the spread and intensities of capabilities across an innovation system, sector or development challenge. For example, if the most typical innovation mode in the agricultural production sector is adoption of technologies developed globally with little modification (Walwyn and Naidoo 2020), but innovation policy instruments and measurement are focused on incentivising new to the world innovation, then there may be significant policy misalignment.

All the indicators proposed can be operationalized, and used for distinctive policy purposes. Government officials may use a composite measure to report high-level progress towards national or global policy intents; while those implementing funding and support programmes on the ground will need analysis of innovation modes that can orient their strategic efforts.

Conclusion

There has long been agreement *that* new innovation indicators are needed to respond to complex development challenges in emerging economies (Rafols 2019; Iizuka and Hollanders 2017; Lepori et al 2008), but this paper contributes to show *how* new indicators can be designed.

A key shift is away from the analytical focus on a national system or priority sector, to a new kind of challenge-oriented, systemic and contextualised indicator scheme. The experimental model suggests a way to measure how innovation policy within a complex socio-technical system (Borras and Edler 2020), across a wide range of industrial sectors and enterprise types, is oriented to change that mitigates pressing socio-economic development challenges, in a manner that is sustainable and inclusive.

Much remains to be operationalised more systematically, and trialled in practice. The design process and indicator scheme was of necessity illustrative of only agricultural production; but, similar iterative processes are planned for the other three sub-systems (Burger 2020) impacting the SDG goal of food security. Although the proposed model is ambitious in scope, it is equally pragmatic, extending and building on standard Oslo-based guidelines, that allow for comparability (OECD 2018).

¹ An item in the AgriBIS assesses current and intended adoption of technologies such as precision agriculture or biometrics.

Indicators of change towards policy intent: Technological upgrading and adoption of advanced technologies, adapted to local climate and environmental conditions, to ‘modernise’ and strengthen existing productive sectors, in order to grow exports and grow jobs, by more firms in the agricultural sector.				
Dimension measured	Indicators	Metrics	Why important	Data sources
1. Sectoral demographics	Size and shape of commercial agricultural sector	Number and size of farms / by income /by employment	Baseline to assess growth of sector	StatsSA Census of Commercial Agriculture 2017
	Spatial distribution of type of farming activity	Number and relative income by province, district, and municipality	Baseline to assess shifts in industrial and territorial inclusiveness	StatsSA
	Size and shape of informal smallholder and household agriculture		Baseline to assess shifts in industrial, territorial and social inclusiveness	National Food and Nutrition Security survey
2. Modernisation of agricultural production	Increased science and technological intensity of ALL agri-production enterprises	Create measure of modes of innovation using variables of novelty, types of activity, over time	Structural transformation, industrial inclusiveness	AgriBIS
	Increased technological capabilities in medium and small enterprises	Mode of innovation disaggregated for SMEs	Industrial inclusiveness	AgriBIS
	Increased technological capabilities in smallholder and household enterprises		Territorial and social inclusiveness	DATA GAP
	Use of digital technologies by enterprises	Use of at least one of a set of advanced technologies by innovative enterprises increases or decreases	Industrial inclusiveness and technology intensity	AgriBIS
	Intent to use digital technologies	Intended use of at least one of a set of advanced technologies by innovative enterprises increases or decreases	Industrial inclusiveness and technology intensity	AgriBIS
3. Strengthen agricultural production system	Improved linkages	Create measure of linkages using variables of sources and collaboration	Technology intensity and industrial inclusiveness	AgriBIS
	Technology transfer from universities	Number and value of diverse forms of technology transfer	Technology intensity, sustainability of agricultural production system	Technology Transfer Office surveys
4. Sustainability of agricultural production	Negative climate effects improved as outcome of innovation	Outcomes variable: Biodiversity Water preservation; Soil fertility Reduced greenhouse gas	Lower wastage and more efficient use of natural resources reflects progress towards sustainability	Agri BIS
5. Growth in Agricultural Exports	Effect of innovation on exports	Increase or decrease of exports over time, and relative to balance of imports	Economic growth and food security	Annual trade data
6. Growth in Agricultural Jobs	Effect of innovation on employment creation	Increase or decrease of jobs over time for innovative enterprises	Structural transformation, Industrial, territorial and social inclusiveness	AgriBIS
		Increase or decrease of jobs spatially and at different levels, over time for all enterprises	As above	StatsSA

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